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2.0	31/03/2025	F. Brunetti	UNITOV	francesca.brunetti@uniroma2.it	Revised draft

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1. Deliverable abstract

This document outlines the dissemination and communication strategy for the JUMP INTO SPACE project. The plan ensures that project results reach key stakeholders, including scientific communities, industries, policymakers, and the general public, following the guidelines set in the Grant Agreement.

2. Objectives

The main objectives of the dissemination and communication activities are:

- To promote project visibility and increase awareness of JUMP INTO SPACE.
- To engage with scientific, industrial, and policy communities.
- To facilitate knowledge transfer and maximize impact.
- To ensure open access to scientific results.
- To comply with EU visibility requirements.
- To actively contribute to the Space Portfolio by engaging with relevant stakeholders and initiatives.

3. Target Audiences

JUMP INTO SPACE dissemination efforts will focus on the following audiences:

- **Scientific Community:** Universities, research institutions, space technology experts.
- **Industry Stakeholders:** Space technology companies, solar energy manufacturers, start-ups.
- **Policy Makers:** European and national space agencies, regulatory bodies.
- **General Public:** Students, young researchers, and citizens interested in space technology.
- **Space Portfolio Community:** Projects and initiatives within the Space Portfolio under the European Innovation Council (EIC).

4. Key Communication and Dissemination Channels

4.1 Internal Communication

- **Mailing list:** A dedicated mailing list has been created including all the involved people from all partners to ensure timely and structured communication among partners, and will be used for project updates, announcements, and document sharing. It is kept up to date by UNITOV.
- **Consortium In-Person Meetings:** organized every 6 months to ensure coordination and alignment across partners.

The kick-off meeting took place in Rome, hosted by UNITOV, in November 2024; the 6M progress meeting will be held in May 2025 in Rome, again hosted by UNITOV, to take advantage of several partners travelling to Rome in the same days for the HOPV2025 conference and to attend the workshop organized by UNITOV at the Italian Space Agency (ASI) headquarters in Rome on the 15th May 2025.

- **Monthly Online Meetings:** scheduled and chaired by UNITOV on Teams. Each partner provides updates on their activities to ensure seamless workflow.
- **Collaborative Platform:** A shared internal repository (Microsoft Teams/ SharePoint) has been created to store and share documents, reports, and deliverables.
- **Instant Communication Channels:** Microsoft Teams can be used for real-time discussions and quick updates among consortium members.

4.2 Online Presence

- **Project Website:** Regular updates on project progress, publications, and events.
- **Social Media:** LinkedIn, X/Twitter, Bluesky for community engagement.
- **Open Access Repositories:** Publishing research papers in repositories such as Zenodo.

4.3 Scientific Dissemination

- **Publications:** Submission of research articles in high-impact journals such as Nature Energy, Advanced Materials, ACS Nano.

<i>Involved partner(s)</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Journal</i>	<i>Submission date</i>	<i>Status (submitted/ accepted)</i>	<i>DOI</i>
HZB	Texture-Enhanced Mechanical Stability of Transparent Electrodes for Flexible Optoelectronics with Near-Infrared Response	Advanced Interface Materials	19/11/2024	Accepted	https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202400922
UNITOV, UNITO	Neutron resilience of flexible perovskite solar cells using PTAA-derived hole transport layers	Solar RRL	27/02/2025	Submitted (under revision)	

- **Participation in Conferences & Workshops:** Participation in HOPV, EU-PVSEC, IEEE PVSC, SPIE Photonics, and ISMSE.
- **Organization of Conferences & Workshops:** organized by one or more of the partners on relevant topics, e.g. one-day workshop organized by UNITOV in Rome and hosted by the Italian Space Agency (ASI) next 15th May 2025.
- **Public Online Webinars:** Organized for interdisciplinary exchange.

<i>Involved partner(s)</i>	<i>Event and venue</i>	<i>Date(s)</i>	<i>Contribution (conference oral or poster, workshop talk, summer school lecture...)</i>	<i>Title</i>
UNITOV	Space PV workshop, Italian Space Agency HQ, Rome (Italy)	15/05/2025	Organization + presentation of the project	Beyond Earth: The Future of Space Solar Energy

4.4 Public Outreach

- **Publications** on newspapers and magazines:

<i>Involved partner(s)</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Magazine, newspaper...</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>link</i>
UNITO, UNITOV, UNISI	“La nuova generazione del fotovoltaico spaziale” (page 130)	Platinum, aziende & protagonisti (n. 082 – attachment to the Italian newspaper Il Sole 24 Ore)	31/03/2025	https://www.calameo.com/read/0033218106e703f1ab712

- **Educational Content:** Development of online lectures and modules for graduate and PhD students.
- **Annual Open Days:** Hands-on workshops for young researchers and students.
- **International Women in STEM Day Event** (February 11): Increasing visibility of women in space technology.

- **Space Portfolio Activities:** Contribution by presenting project advancements and participating in Portfolio-led dissemination efforts. Participation in working groups (mainly WG1 – Solar Cells, where UNITOV is WG leader) and related communication & dissemination activities.

4.5 Industry and Policy Engagement

- **Trade Fairs:** Presence at Intersolar, SPACEPV, and ESPC.
- **Stakeholder Matchmaking Events:** Facilitating collaboration with space agencies (ESA, ASI).
- **Policy Briefs & White Papers:** Recommendations for future funding and regulations.
- **Space Portfolio Meetings:** Participation in working groups (mainly WG1 – Solar Cells, where UNITOV is WG leader) and coordination meetings and joint activities within the Space Portfolio.

5. Implementation Timeline

Activity	Lead Partner	Month Due
<i>Website launch & updates</i>	UNITOV	M2 & ongoing
<i>Social media updates</i>	UNITOV	Monthly
<i>Scientific publications</i>	All partners	M6, M12, M24, M36, M48
<i>Conference participation</i>	All partners	M12, M24, M36, M48
<i>Industry trade fair presence</i>	SAULE	M18, M36
<i>Policy engagement events</i>	UNITOV, ONERA	M12, M30
<i>Public outreach events</i>	UNITOV	M12, M24, M48
<i>Space Portfolio coordination meetings</i>	UNITOV	M6, M18, M36
<i>Portfolio reports and contributions</i>	UNITOV	M12, M24, M48

6. Monitoring & Evaluation

To ensure effective dissemination, JUMP INTO SPACE will implement the following KPIs:

- **Website Traffic:** Targeting >200 visits/year.
- **Social Media Engagement:** >50 shares/interactions per post.
- **Scientific Output:** Minimum 3 open-access publications per partner.
- **Conference Attendance:** At least 2 major conferences per partner.
- **Events for a general, non-specialized audience:** At least 2 workshops and one final event.
- **Space Portfolio Participation:** Minimum 3 contributions to Portfolio activities per year.

7. Intellectual Property Considerations

To ensure that potentially exploitable commercial results are adequately protected, dissemination activities will be reviewed for intellectual property (IP) concerns. Partners will assess project findings before public release to determine whether any results require patent applications, trade secrets, or other IP protections.

A dedicated exploitation plan will handle commercial pathways, and any restricted findings will be shared only with authorized stakeholders under confidentiality agreements.

8. Compliance with EU Regulations

All dissemination materials will include the EU emblem and funding acknowledgment:

European
Innovation
Council

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the EIC under GA n. 101162377.

9. Conclusions

This plan provides a structured framework to maximize the impact of JUMP INTO SPACE. The plan will be reviewed and updated periodically to adapt to project progress and stakeholder needs.

